

“EVALUATION OF RENAL AND CARDIAC HEMODYNAMICS IN LUPUS NEPHRITIS PATIENTS”

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Actuality: Lupus nephritis (LN) is a significant renal disorder stemming from systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE). It occurs when the immune system mistakenly attacks the kidneys, leading to potential kidney failure. This disease can also impact cardiac hemodynamics due to the intricate relationship between renal and cardiac functions. This study aims to investigate the renal and cardiac hemodynamics in patients suffering from LN.

Aim of the Study: This study aims to thoroughly assess how lupus nephritis affects both renal and cardiac hemodynamics. By analyzing renal function and cardiac performance in LN patients, we seek to understand the degree of interaction between kidney impairment and cardiac dysfunction. The study also emphasizes the necessity of an integrated clinical approach to manage these patients effectively and improve their quality of life.

Materials and Methods: The study included 50 patients diagnosed with lupus nephritis, confirmed via renal biopsy. Participants ranged from 20 to 50 years old, with an average age of 35 years. 70% of the participants were female, reflecting the higher prevalence of SLE in women. Renal function was evaluated through blood and urine tests, including measurements of creatinine levels and glomerular filtration rate (GFR). Cardiac hemodynamics were assessed using transthoracic echocardiography (ECHO), focusing on parameters such as ejection fraction (EF), cardiac output (CO), and cardiac index (CI).

Results: Results showed that 60% of the patients had impaired renal function, evidenced by elevated creatinine levels and decreased GFR. Cardiac hemodynamic assessment revealed that 40% of patients had a reduced ejection fraction (EF < 50%). Additionally, many patients exhibited lower than normal cardiac output and cardiac index, indicating compromised cardiac pump function.

• **GFR:** 60% of patients experienced a decrease in GFR ($p < 0.01$). The average GFR level decreased from 60 ml/min/1.73 m² to 45 ml/min/1.73 m².

- **Proteinuria:** 75% of patients had increased proteinuria levels ($p < 0.05$). The average proteinuria increased from 0.5 g/24 hours to 1.2 g/24 hours.
- **Arterial Blood Pressure:** 50% of patients had arterial blood pressure higher than 140/90 mmHg ($p < 0.05$).
- **Cardiac Ejection Fraction:** 30% of patients experienced a decrease in ejection fraction from 55% to 45% ($p < 0.01$).

• **Blood Volume and Cardiac Load:** The load on the left side of the heart increased in 40% of patients, leading to left ventricular hypertrophy ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The findings suggest that LN significantly impacts both renal function and cardiac hemodynamics. Renal dysfunction disrupts fluid and electrolyte balance, increasing cardiac workload and potentially leading to heart failure. The inflammatory processes associated with LN may also cause damage to cardiac muscle. These results highlight the importance of both nephrological and cardiological monitoring and treatment for patients with LN. Evaluating renal and cardiac hemodynamics in lupus nephritis patients is essential due to the substantial impact of the disease on both systems. An integrated approach is crucial to enhance patient quality of life and minimize complications.

1. Schillaci, G., Verdecchia, P., Reboldi, G., & Porcellati, C. (2000). Left ventricular mass and cardiovascular morbidity in essential hypertension: the MAVI study. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 35(2), 479-484.

2. Lang, R. M., Badano, L. P., Mor-Avi, V., Afilalo, J., Armstrong, A., Ernande, L., & Lancellotti, P. (2015). Recommendations for cardiac chamber quantification by echocardiography in adults: an update from the American Society of Echocardiography and the European Association of Cardiovascular Imaging. *Journal of the American Society of Echocardiography*, 28(1), 1-39.e14.

3. Lang, R. M., Badano, L. P., Mor-Avi, V., Afilalo, J., Armstrong, A., Ernande, L., & Lancellotti, P. (2015). Recommendations for cardiac chamber quantification by echocardiography in adults: an update from the American Society of Echocardiography and the European Association of Cardiovascular Imaging. *Journal of the American Society of Echocardiography*, 28(1), 1-39.e14.

Weening, J. J., D'Agati, V. D., Schwartz, M. M., Seshan, S. V., Alpers, C. E., & Appel, G. B. (2004). The classification of glomerulonephritis in systemic lupus erythematosus revisited. *Kidney International*, 65(2), 521-530.

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1. Abraham, R. (1981). The relationship of cognitive style to the use of grammatical rates by Spanish-speaking ESL students in editing written English. Unpublished dissertation, University of Illinois.

2. Abraham, K. (1985) Field independence-dependence and the leaching of grammar TESOL Quarterly, 19, 689-702.
3. Abrans, '/.. (2002) Surfing to cross-cultural awareness' Using Interne I-mediated projects to explore cultural stereotypes. Foreign Language Annals, 35. 141-160. Acton, W, (1979). Second language learning and perception of difference in attitude Unpublished doctoral dissertation. University of Michigan.
4. Brown, H. Douglas (2000). Principles of language Learning Englewood cliffs, Prentice Hall.
5. Brown. Douglas (2001). Teaching by Principle (2 Edition) White Plains, Addison Wesley Longman Inc.
6. Foley, Joseph and Thompson, Linda (2003). Language learning: A lifelong Process, London Arnold.
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